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Examination of Education Quality Perceptions of Physical Education and Sports School Students (Bayburt University School of Physical Education and Sports Example)

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Abstract

This study aims to measure the perceptions of students of Bayburt University School of Physical Education and Sports about the quality of education at the institution where they study and to investigate whether there is a difference between perceptions of students about the quality of education concerning different variables. This study is a descriptive study designed using the scanning model. The study population consists of 673 students continuing their education in 2020-2021 at Bayburt University School of Physical Education and sports. The sample consists of 276 students studying in this institution. The scale Physical Education and Sports Sciences Performance in Universities Providing Physical Education and Sports Education (PESPERF) developed by Paktaş (2015) for the School of Physical Education and Sports students was used for the study. The analysis of data was carried out using SPSS 25.0 package program. The significance tests were based on a significance level of 0.05 (p). Independent samples t-test (Independent Samples T-test), one-way analysis of variance (One Way ANOVA) for unrelated samples with more than two means, and tests for correlation analysis were used to analyze the data concerning the sub-dimensions. Before the research was carried out, permission was obtained from Ethics Committee of Bayburt University. As a result of the analysis, a significant difference was found in favor of male students in all sub-dimensions except manager's vision according to the gender variable. Consequently, it can be said that the variable of gender, have a significant influence on individual perceptions of educational quality

Keywords: Physical Education and Sports, Education, Quality, Education Quality

1. Introduction

If we examine the origin of the word education, it is the equivalent of the Latin words 'educare' and 'educere' (Billington, 1997). In our country, the term 'education' has been used since the first quarter of the 20th century with words such as instruction, training, and schooling (Başaran, 1984). In examining the literature, Ertürk (1979) defined the concept of education as the process that brings about desired changes in a person's actions

and attitudes through his own life (Ertürk, 1979). In addition, Şişman (2001) defines education as a set of planned effects that contribute to achieving specific improvements in the individual's behavior based on the principles established at the beginning, while Özden (2002) defines it as an education that contributes to social competence and ideal personal development through the effect of a particular and controlled environment. One of the most important branches of this education is physical education.

In this interaction, the combination of physiological, social, and psychological movements and physical education is defined as the element that serves as a tool rather than a goal (Kul, 2008). Yaylacı (1998) defined this element as ensuring the individual's physical, emotional, and mental development following the Basic Principles of National Education. Physical education is not only an integral and inseparable part of education but also of personality education. Considering the individual differences, physical education is a vital tool to educate individuals with healthy, happy, moral, compassionate, constructive, creative, productive, national cultural values and behaviors necessary for a democratic life (Güneş, 2004).

The strength of a country is as great as the abilities of the people who live in it. In this context, the higher the quality of education in the society, the greater the country's capacity. Therefore, the vision of educational institutions increases the quality of services they provide to individuals (Keskin and Keskin, 2005). We can define quality as "an institution's awareness of what service it provides to whom and its continuous improvement to raise the quality of that service to the level of the best examples in the world and even beyond" (Demirhan, 2011). On the other hand, quality in education is the realization of education following its goals and conditions. Knowing the needs of students and implementing programs that are aligned with those needs. It is the result of educators' ability to co-create education and future lives of students. (Egitimpedia, 2021). The quality of education can be improved through collaborative programs in technology, social and cultural environments, human resources, and student support. (Adatepe, 2018).

The opportunities and chances given to students in educating our youth, who are the guarantee of our future, are of great importance to the quality of education. In this direction, the study aims to carry out activities to increase the quality of education, such as identifying the current situation and recommendations with the studies to be carried out in this area.

2. Methodology

2.1. Study Objective

This study aims to measure the perceptions of students of Bayburt University School of Physical Education and Sports about the quality of education at the institution where they study and to investigate whether there is a difference between perceptions of students about the quality of education concerning different variables.

2.2. Research Model

This study is a descriptive study designed using the scanning model. Karasar (2014) referred to the survey model as a research approach that aims to describe a past or present situation as it is.

2.3. Research Sample

The study population consists of 673 students continuing their education in 2020-2021 at Bayburt University School of Physical Education and sports. The sample consists of 276 students studying in this institution.

2.4. Data Collection Tools and Procedure

The scale Physical Education and Sports Sciences Performance in Universities Providing Physical Education and Sports Education (PESPERF) developed by Paktaş (2015) for the School of Physical Education and Sports students was used for the study. The Cronbach Alpha value of the PESPERF scale developed by Paktaş (2015)

was reported as 0.908. Looking at the sub-dimensions, there was a value of $\alpha=0.840$ for the sub-dimension Physical Conditions (question 5, 12, 15, 17, 23, 39), a value of $\alpha=0.940$ for the sub-dimension Leadership Characteristics (question 2, 8, 20, 27, 38, 41, 42, 46, 50, 56, 59, 61, 64), a value of $\alpha=0.910$ for the sub-dimension vision of the manager (question 1, 9, 10, 28, 60), a value of $\alpha=0.940$ for the sub-dimension trainer's characteristics (question 4, 16, 21, 29, 34, 35, 43, 47, 49, 51, 63), a value of $\alpha=0.920$ for the sub-dimension Training Programs (question 3, 22, 26, 30, 36, 44, 45, 53, 55, 58), a value of $\alpha=0.890$ for Teaching Methods (question 6, 11, 14, 19, 33, 40, 48), a value of $\alpha=0.900$ for the measurement and evaluation sub-dimension (question 25, 32, 52, 54), a value of $\alpha=0.920$ for the support services sub-dimension (question 7, 13, 18, 24, 31, 37, 57, 62) (Paktaş, 2015).

This study reported that KMO and Barlett's test results were 0.961, and Barlett's test was significant ($p<.001$). This is the value and the test that explains whether the sample is sufficient for the analysis. When analyzing the scale's reliability, the Cronbach Alpha value $\alpha=0.981$ shows that it is highly reliable. When the Cronbach Alpha value of the sub-dimensions of the scale is examined, it indicates that Physical Conditions $\alpha=0.866$, Leadership Characteristics $\alpha=0.934$, the vision of the manager $\alpha=0.796$, characteristics of the trainer $\alpha=0.916$, training programs $\alpha=0.892$, teaching methods $\alpha=0.851$, measurement, and evaluation $\alpha=0.835$, and the support services $\alpha=0.874$.

2.5. Data Analysis

The analysis of data was carried out using SPSS 25.0 package program.

In a statistical study, the distribution should be normal or close to normal to perform many tests. Since the data is far from a normal distribution, the analysis results are wrong, and so are the interpretations. Tabachnick and Fidell (2013) assume that the distribution is normal if the skewness and kurtosis values are between +1,500 and -1,500. Since the values for skewness (-.831) and kurtosis (.954) of these scale expressions are between +1.500 and -1.500, we can say that the distribution is normal in our study. For this reason, analysis tests that can be performed with a normal distribution were performed in our research.

The significance tests were based on a significance level of 0.05 (p). Independent samples t-test (Independent Samples T-test), one-way analysis of variance (One Way ANOVA) for unrelated samples with more than two means, and tests for correlation analysis were used to analyze the data concerning the sub-dimensions.

2.6. Ethical

Before the research was carried out, permission was obtained from Ethics Committee of Bayburt University (Date: 09.06.2020, Number of Sessions: 2020/42).

3. Findings

Table 1: Frequency and Percentages of Demographic Variables

Variable	Group	N	%
Gender	Female	93	33.7
	Male	183	66.3
Grade	1st Grade	88	31.9
	2nd Grade	72	26.1
	3rd Grade	56	20.3
	4th Grade	60	21.7
Department	Physical Education and Sports Teaching	39	14.1
	Coaching Education	170	61.6
	Sports Management	67	24.3
Place of Residence	Village	46	16.7
	District	91	33.0
	Province	77	27.9
	Metropolis	62	22.5
Socioeconomic Status	Low	44	15.9
	Middle	210	76.1
	High	22	8.0
Education Status of the Mother	Primary School	196	71.0
	Secondary School	45	16.3
	High School	17	6.2
	Associate Degree	7	2.5
	Undergraduate Degree	11	4.0
Education Status of the Father	Primary School	130	47.1
	Secondary School	75	27.2
	High School	46	16.7
	Associate Degree	7	2.5
	Undergraduate Degree	16	5.8
The Type of High School of Graduation	Open Education High School	3	1.1
	Anatolian High School	101	36.6
	Anatolian Imam Hatip High School	40	14.5
	Multi-Program Anatolian High School	24	8.7
	Vocational and Technical	60	21.7
	Anatolian High School		
	Social sciences High School	1	0.4
Other	47	17.0	

Table 1 shows the frequency and percentages of students who participated in the study according to the different variables. 93 (33.7%) of the 276 students who participated in the study were female, and 183 (66.3%) were male. According to the grade variable of the students, 88 persons (31.9%) participated from 1st grade, 72 persons (26.1%) participated from 2nd grade, 56 persons (20.3%) participated from 3rd grade, and 60 persons (21.7%) participated from 4th grade). Looking at the distribution of students according to the department they study, 39 (14.1%) out of 276 students are Physical Education and Sports Teaching, 170 (61.6%) Coaching Education, and 67 (24.3%) Sports Management Department. Looking at the distribution of students according to the variable socioeconomic level, 44 students (15.9%) are at a low socioeconomic level, 210 students (76.1%) are at a medium socioeconomic level, and 22 students (8%) are at a high socioeconomic level. A high percentage of participants reported being in the middle socioeconomic status. Looking at the distribution of students according to the variable of mother's education level, 196 (71%) have primary school graduates, 45 (16.3%) have secondary school graduates, 17 (6.2%) have a high school graduates, 7 have an associate degree graduates (2.5%) and bachelor's degree graduates can be seen that there are 11 (4%) persons. Looking at the distribution of students by father's educational level, it is found that 130 (47.1%) are primary school graduates, 75 (27.2%) are secondary school graduates, 46 (16.7%) are high school graduates, 7 (2.5%) are associate degree graduates, and 16 (5.8%) are bachelor's degree graduates. Looking at the type of high school from which students graduated, there are 3 (1.1%) open high schools, 101 (36.6%) Anatolian high schools, 40 (14.5%) Imam Hatip Anatolian

high schools, 24 (8.7%) multi-program Anatolian high schools, 60 (21.7%) vocational and technical Anatolian high schools, 1 (0.4%) social science high school, and 47 (17%) graduates from other high schools. Looking at the variable of the place of residence of the students participating in the study, it is found that 46 (16.7%) live in the village, 91 (33%) in the district, 77 (27.9%) in the province, and 62 (22.5%) in the metropolitan area. It was also found that the average age of the students participating in the study is 21.97 years.

Table 2: Arithmetic Mean and Standard Deviation Values of Scale Sub-Dimensions

Sub-Dimension No	Sub-Dimension Name	n	$\bar{X}$	SS
1	Physical Conditions	276	3.04	1.096
2	Leadership Characteristics	276	3.51	.906
3	Manager's Vision	276	3.73	.850
4	Trainer's Characteristics	276	3.52	.880
5	Training Programs	276	3.43	.863
6	Teaching Methods	276	3.70	.831
7	Measurement and Evaluation	276	3.32	.975
8	Support Services	276	3.05	.976

When the arithmetic mean of participants' scores from the sub-dimensions of the scale is examined in Table 2, it is seen that the highest score is in the sub-dimension of "Manager's Vision."

Table 3: The t-test on Quality Perception Levels of Students by Gender Variables

Sub-Dimensions	Gender	n	$\bar{X}$	SS	t	P
Physical Conditions	Female	93	2.59	.949	-5.304	.000*
	Male	183	3.29	1.091		
Leadership Characteristics	Female	93	3.26	.893	-3.318	.001*
	Male	183	3.64	.889		
Manager's Vision	Female	93	3.62	.829	-1.480	.140
	Male	183	3.78	.858		
Trainer's Characteristics	Female	93	3.31	.827	-2.761	.006*
	Male	183	3.62	.889		
Training Programs	Female	93	3.18	.843	-3.554	.000*
	Male	183	3.56	.846		
Teaching Methods	Female	93	3.52	.834	-2.591	.010*
	Male	183	3.79	.817		
Measurement and Evaluation	Female	93	3.18	.900	-3.856	.000*
	Male	183	3.65	.976		
Support Services	Female	93	2.69	.803	-4.375	.000*
	Male	183	3.22	1.010		

*p<0.05

Looking at the results in Table 3, the results of the t-test for independent groups conducted to determine whether the sub-dimensions of the scale on the perception of the quality of the school that students attend have a statistically significant difference depending on the gender variable, there are statistically significant differences in the other sub-dimensions of the scale, except for the "manager's vision" ($p < 0.05$). Looking at the arithmetic means, we can say that this difference is generally in favor of the male students.

Table 4: ANOVA Test on Quality Perception Levels of Students by Grade Variable

Sub-Dimensions	Grade	N	$\bar{X}$	Ss	F	p	Scheffe Test
Physical Conditions	1st Grade	88	3.45	.105	7.885	.000*	1-2 1-3
	2nd Grade	72	2.86	.124			
	3rd Grade	56	2.63	.153			
	4th Grade	60	3.11	.137			
Leadership Characteristics	1st Grade	88	3.80	.724	5.632	.001*	1-3
	2nd Grade	72	3.41	.859			
	3rd Grade	56	3.21	1.087			
	4th Grade	60	3.49	.919			
Manager's Vision	1st Grade	88	4.01	.620	5.572	.001*	1-3
	2nd Grade	72	3.68	.777			
	3rd Grade	56	3.50	1.043			
	4th Grade	60	3.59	.932			
Trainer's Characteristics	1st Grade	88	3.77	.763	7.494	.000*	1-3 2-3
	2nd Grade	72	3.62	.775			
	3rd Grade	56	3.12	1.064			
	4th Grade	60	3.39	.833			
Training Programs	1st Grade	88	3.66	.817	4.779	.003*	1-3
	2nd Grade	72	3.38	.749			
	3rd Grade	56	3.12	1.019			
	4th Grade	60	3.44	.817			
Teaching Methods	1st Grade	88	3.83	.730	2.657	.052	-
	2nd Grade	72	3.70	.796			
	3rd Grade	56	3.44	1.020			
	4th Grade	60	3.75	.783			
Measurement and Evaluation	1st Grade	88	3.74	.893	5,475	.001*	1-3
	2nd Grade	72	3.47	.890			
	3rd Grade	56	3.08	1.082			
	4th Grade	60	3.52	.980			
Support Services	1st Grade	88	3.31	.975	5.138	.002*	1-3
	2nd Grade	72	2.95	.955			
	3rd Grade	56	2.68	.974			
	4th Grade	60	3.09	.906			

*p<0.05

As can be seen in Table 4, as a result of the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) of the PESPERF sub-dimensions with the students' grade variable, a statistically significant difference was found in the other sub-dimensions of the scale, except for "Teaching Methods" (p 0.05). Scheffe's test for multiple comparisons was used for the sub-dimensions where the difference occurred. When the results of Scheffe's test are analyzed at the sub-dimension level, the difference in the sub-dimension "Physical Conditions" between the 1st and 2nd grade ($\bar{x}=3.45 - \bar{x}=2.86$) is in favor of the 1st grade and between the 1st and 3rd grade ($\bar{x}=3.45 - \bar{x}=2.63$) is in favor of the 3rd grade. In the sub-dimension "Leadership Characteristics," a significant difference is found between 1st and 3rd grade ($\bar{x}=3.80 - \bar{x}=3.21$) in favor of 1st grade. In the sub-dimension "Manager's vision," there is a significant difference between the 1st and 3rd grades ($\bar{x}=4.01 - \bar{x}=3.50$) in favor of the 1st grade. In the sub-dimension "Trainer's Characteristics," there is a significant difference between the 1st and 3rd grades ($\bar{x}=3.77 - \bar{x}=3.12$) in favor of the 1st grade, while between the 2nd and 3rd grade ($\bar{x}=3.62 - \bar{x}=3.12$) there is a significant difference in favor of the 2nd grade. In the sub-dimension "Training Programs," there is a significant difference between 1st and 3rd grade ($\bar{x}=3.66 - \bar{x}=3.12$) in favor of 1st grade. In the sub-dimension "Measurement and Evaluation," there is a significant difference between 1st and 3rd grade ($\bar{x}=3.74 - \bar{x}=3.08$) in favor of 1st grade. In

the sub-dimension "Support Services," there is a significant difference between 1st and 3rd grade ($\bar{x}=3.31$ - $\bar{x}=2.68$) in favor of 1st grade.

Table 5: ANOVA Test Related to the Quality Perception Levels of Students According to the Variable

Sub-Dimensions	SED	N	$\bar{x}$	Ss	F	p	Scheffe
Physical Conditions	Low (1)	44	2.71	1.035	3.060	0.050	—
	Medium (2)	210	3.10	1.097			
	High (3)	22	3.33	1.097			
Leadership Characteristics	Low (1)	44	3.08	.878	8.611	0,001*	1-2
	Medium (2)	210	3.56	.902			
	High (3)	22	3.97	.664			
Manager's Vision	Low (1)	44	3.31	.869	7,499	.001*	1-2 1-3
	Medium (2)	210	3.78	.833			
	High (3)	22	4.04	.724			
Trainer's Characteristics	Low (1)	44	3.08	.883	7.718	.001*	1-3
	Medium (2)	210	3.58	.862			
	High (3)	22	3.83	.767			
Training Programs	Low (1)	44	2.97	.942	8.914	.000*	1-2
	Medium (2)	210	3.49	.831			
	High (3)	22	3.76	.684			
Teaching Methods	Low (1)	44	3.28	.995	8,378	.000*	1-2 1-3
	Medium (2)	210	3.75	.784			
	High (3)	22	4.04	.617			
Measurement and Evaluation	Low (1)	44	3.00	.922	9.709	.000*	1-2
	Medium (2)	210	3.54	.968			
	High (3)	22	4.03	.753			
Support Services	Low (1)	44	2.56	.902	7.371	.001*	1-3
	Medium (2)	210	3.11	.959			
	High (3)	22	3.36	1.017			

*p<0.05

In Table 5, as a result of the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) performed between the sub-dimensions of the PESPERF scale and the quotient variable, a statistically significant difference is found for the other sub-dimensions, except for the sub-dimension "Physical Conditions" ($p<0.05$). The Scheffé test was used for multiple comparisons to check which departments this difference exists. For the sub-dimension "Leadership Characteristics," a significant difference is found between low and medium socioeconomic levels ($\bar{x}=3.08$ - $\bar{x}=3.56$) in favor of the medium socioeconomic level. For the sub-dimension "Manager's Vision" the difference between low and medium socioeconomic levels ($\bar{x}=3.31$ - $\bar{x}=3.78$) in favor of medium socioeconomic level), between low and high socioeconomic level ($\bar{x}=3.31$ - $\bar{x}=4.04$) in favor of high socioeconomic level is significant. For the sub-dimension "Trainer's Characteristics" there is a significant difference between low and high socioeconomic levels ($\bar{x}=3.08$ - $\bar{x}=3.83$), in favor of high socioeconomic levels. For the sub-dimension "Training Programs" there is a significant difference between low and medium socioeconomic levels ($\bar{x}=2.97$ - $\bar{x}=3.49$) in favor of medium socioeconomic levels. In the sub-dimension "Measurement and Evaluation," there is a significant difference between low and medium socioeconomic levels ($\bar{x}=3.00$ - $\bar{x}=3.54$), in favor of medium socioeconomic level. In the sub-dimension "Support Services," there is a significant difference between a low and a high socioeconomic level ($\bar{x}=2.56$ - $\bar{x}=3.36$) in favor of the high socioeconomic level.

Table 6: Correlation Analysis of Students' Age Variable and Sub-Dimensions of the Scale

N=276	Age	Physical Conditions	Leadership Characteristics	Manager' s Vision	Trainer's Characteristics	Training Programs	Teaching Methods	Measurement and Evaluation	Support Services
Age	1	.049	.005	-.061	-.029	-.003	.053	.030	.044
p		.420	.931	.315	.634	.963	.376	.615	.468

As shown in Table 6, the Pearson correlation analysis conducted to determine the relationship between the sub-dimensions of the PESPERF scale and the students' age variable did not reveal a statistically significant relationship between age and all sub-dimensions on the scale ($p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$).

Table 7: Correlation Analysis of the location of the Student Residence Variable and the Sub-Dimensions of the Scale

N=276	Place of Residence	Physical Conditions	Leadership Characteristics	Manager' s Vision	Trainer's Characteristics	Training Programs	Teaching Methods	Measurement and Evaluation	Support Services
Place of Residence	1	.122*	.082	.085	.060	.040	.106	.050	.052
p		.043	.176	.159	.324	.510	.079	.406	.385

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$

As can be seen in Table 7, as a result of the Pearson correlation analysis conducted to determine the relationship between the sub-dimensions of the PESPERF scale and the variable of the student's location, a positive, weak, and positive statistically significant relationship was found only for the sub-dimension "Physical Conditions ($r = .122$, $p < 0.05$)" which is one of the sub-dimensions of the scale.

4. Discussion, Conclusion, and Recommendations

Examination of the student's responses to the scale concerning the sub-dimensions revealed that the mean scores ranged from 3.04 to 3.73. From this point of view, it can be said that the student's perception of the quality of education is at a medium level.

It was found that there was a difference in favor of male students in the sub-dimensions Physical Education and Sports Sciences Performance Scale for Physical Education and Sports School students. The gender variable was obtained in the sub-dimensions physical conditions, leadership qualities, trainer's characteristics, training programs, teaching methods, measurement and evaluation, and support services. It can be said that male students place more importance on the quality of education they receive than female students. Considering the studies that reached similar results to our study, Adatepe and Kul (2021) in their study found a difference in favor of male students in the sub-dimensions of physical conditions and assessment and evaluation. Çavuşoğlu and Sağlam (2021) also found a difference in favor of male students in the sub-dimension of physical conditions. On the other hand, Paktaş (2015), Boz and Kiremitçi (2018) did not find any significant difference in their studies concerning the variable of gender. Cohen et al. (1996) state that the physical environment is the skeleton of learning and can promote learning and hinder learning (cited by Polat and Discovery-Kırıkkaya, 2004). Being competent means that the leader has the necessary knowledge, skills, and attitudes to perform his/her tasks following organizational goals (Kayıkçı, 2001; Onural, 2005). Reviewing the literature, one finds that there are

studies that aim to determine the quality of education in higher education institutions by considering one or more of these variables (Ensari and Onur, 2003; Tüzün and Devrani, 2008; Şahin, 2009; Sökmen, 2011). In these studies, it has been shown that teacher quality has an essential place in the quality of education (Yıldırım et al., 2018). Qualified programs are needed to increase the quality of education in the field of education. In universities, lecturers have the task of educating their students through educational programs with the quality required by society (Kalaycı, 2008). According to Temel (1988), teaching methods, one of the curriculum elements, occupy an important place in the efficient implementation of teaching and learning activities (cited in Yüksel, 2008). Undoubtedly, there has been a need for measurement and assessment in every period of education, and attempts have been made to determine student achievement with committee decisions, teacher opinions, examinations, portfolios, and many other instruments we cannot name (Başol et al., 2013). Measurement and evaluation, an integral part of the teaching process, is used to determine student achievement and deficits, understand the effectiveness of teaching methods, and reveal the curriculum's strengths and weaknesses (MEB, 2004; Birgin & Gürbüz, 2008). On the other hand, support services can be defined as "any service that facilitates learners' work at any stage of a curriculum" (Bozkurt, 2013). Based on this information, it can be said that male students care about some details of the physical conditions and pay attention to the qualifications of the head of the institution. It can be said that female students are more satisfied with the adequacy of educational programs, teaching methods used by the instructor during the course, measurement and evaluation methods used, and some support services (such as cultural and sports activities) that should be provided in educational institutions. And in this context, it can be said that the perception of the quality of education is higher.

There were between the 1st grade and the 2nd grade and the 3rd grade in favor of the first grade, between the 1st grade and the 3rd grade in the subdimension Leadership Characteristics in favor of the 1st-grade difference in the subdimension Physical Conditions between the subdimensions Physical Education and Sports Sciences Performance in Universities Providing Physical Education and Sports Education of the participants and the grade variables. In the subdimension vision of the leader between the 1st and 3rd grades, in favor of the 1st grades, in the subdimension trainer's characteristics between the 1st and 3rd grades in favor of the 1st grades and between the 2nd and 3rd grades. In the sub-dimension measurement and evaluation, there is a difference in favor of the 1st grade between the 1st and 3rd grades and a difference in favor of the 1st grade between the 1st and 3rd grades in the support services sub-dimension has been reached. It can be said that 1st-grade students have a higher perception of education quality than 2nd and 3rd-grade students. Similarly, Çavuşoğlu and Sağlam (2021) concluded in their study that 1st-grade students performed better than 4th-grade students in the Support Services sub-dimension. Adatepe and Kul (2021) found that 4th-grade students have a higher perception of quality than the other grades. In the study conducted by Paktaş (2015), the 2nd-grade students in the research group were trained in the sub-dimensions of physical conditions, leadership characteristics, leader, training programs, measurement and evaluation, and support services according to the variable "Students' Grade" which determines their perception of the quality of education. They were found to have a higher perception of quality than 3rd and 4th-grade students. It can be said that the result of our study is that first-year students are more willing because they have just started their university education and the quality of education they perceive is in line with their expectations.

In the subdimension leadership characteristics of the participants, between the subdimensions of Education Quality Scale on the Universities Providing Physical Education and Sports Education for the students of the School of Physical Education and Sports and the variable of socioeconomic level, there was a difference in favor of the medium level between the medium level and the low level. In the manager's vision sub-dimension, there was a difference between the medium level and the low level in favor of the medium level, between the high level and the low level in favor of the high level. In the trainer's characteristics sub-dimension, there was a difference between the high level and the low level in favor of the high level. In the training programs sub-dimension, there was a difference between medium and low in favor of medium, in the teaching methods sub-dimension in favor of medium, and between high and low in favor of high. In the measurement and evaluation sub-dimension, a difference was found between medium and low in favor of medium and the support services sub-dimension, between high and low in favor of high. It can be seen that 15.9% of the students who participated in our study were from low socioeconomic classes, 76.1% were from medium socioeconomic classes, and 8%

were from high socioeconomic classes. Buchta (2009), in his study, found that 12% of students who participated in physical education were from low socioeconomic class, 47% were from middle socioeconomic class, and 41% were from high socioeconomic class. Adatepe's (2018) study revealed that 8.1% of the students were from low socioeconomic class, 73.4% were from medium socioeconomic class, and 18.5% were from high socioeconomic class. Paktaş (2015), in his study, concluded that students with high socioeconomic levels have a higher perception of educational quality than other socioeconomic levels. Adatepe and Kul (2021), in their study, concluded that students with high socioeconomic status perceive the quality of education they receive at the institution where they study as higher. In line with this information, it can be said that the tendency of students with low socioeconomic status to go into business to complete their education as soon as possible and strengthen their financial situation, rather than the quality of education they receive, is the cause of this difference.

No statistically significant relationship was found between the subdimensions of Physical Education and Sports Sciences Performance in Universities Providing Physical Education and Sports Education and the age variable. In contrast to our study, Adatepe and Kul (2021) found a negative relationship between the age variable and the sub-dimensions of "Leadership Characteristics, Leader's Vision, Trainer's Characteristics, Training Programs, Measurement and Evaluation" in their study. They find that the perception of the quality of the above dimensions (Leadership Characteristics, Leader's Vision, Trainer's Characteristics, Training Programs, Measurement and Evaluation) decreases as the student's age increases. Çavuşoğlu and Sağlam (2021) find in their study that the higher age group has lower educational quality on average because they can evaluate educational programs better with increasing age and experience. In our study, it can be said that the age variable did not cause any change in students' perception of educational quality.

A positive and weak relationship was found between physical conditions and the variable of residence, which is one of the sub-dimensions of Physical Education and Sports Sciences Performance in Universities Providing Physical Education and Sports Education. Education is a multidimensional phenomenon that develops under the influence of many factors. The physical conditions of educational buildings, one of these factors, play a critical role in the quality of education (Al Şensoy & Sağsöz, 2015). According to Uludağ and Odacı (2002), "physical environment refers to the characteristics of the space reserved for educational activities. Some factors such as desks, tables, cabinets, etc., empty spaces, warmth, light, and the color scheme of the space constitute the variables of the physical environment. The relationships between teachers and students are greatly influenced by these physical variables (Aydın, 1988). According to Al Şensoy and Sağsöz (2015), it is claimed that the physical conditions of educational buildings directly or indirectly influence student performance (Lackney, 1999; Lyons 2001; Edward, 2006; Vandier, 2011). In this context, it can be said that as students move from village to district, from district to city, from province to metropolis, they begin to attach more importance to the physical environment of the institution where they study. This situation influences their perception of educational quality.

Consequently, it can be said that the variables of gender, place of residence, grade, place of residence, and socioeconomic level have a significant influence on individual perceptions of educational quality. It was found that students perceived the education they received at Bayburt University School of Physical Education and sports as mediocre in all sub-dimensions of the scale. In line with this result, it is considered that it is beneficial for the institution concerned to undertake activities to improve the quality of education to make it a point of attraction for students who may prefer that institution in the future.

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